

Table 4.1: Participant profile questions.

ID	Question	Scale of response
Q1	What is your age?	Under 21; between 21 and 25; between 26 and 30; between 31 and 35; between 36 and 40 years; between 41 and 45 years; between 46 and 50 years; between 51 and 55 years; between 56 and 60 years; over 60 years.
Q2	Which state do you live in?	AC; AL; AP; AM; BA; CE; DF; ES; GO; MA; MT; MS; MG; PA; PB; PR; PE; PI; RJ; RN; RS; RO; RR; SC; SP; SE; TO.
Q3	What is your level of education?	Undergraduate; graduate; specialization; master's; doctorate.
Q4	In which stage of software development do you work professionally?	Requirements elicitation; data analysis; systems modeling; development/programming; testing; software maintenance and evolution; other.
Q5	What is the nature of the organization you work for?	Private company; Federal Public Administration agency; Research/collaboration project; State-owned company (BB, CEF, SERPRO, DATAPREV); Open-source software project; Self-employed.
Q6	How long have you been working in software development?	Less than 1 year; between 1 and 3 years; between 4 and 6 years; between 7 and 9 years; between 10 and 15 years; over 16 years.
Q7	With regard to data privacy, are you familiar with the General Data Protection Law (LGPD)?	Likert scale (totally agree; agree; neither agree nor disagree; disagree; totally disagree).

Table 4.2: Questions relating to the participants' challenges.

ID	Question	Scale of response
Q8	Check which of the challenges listed below you face in your organization to ensure compliance with privacy legislation.	Checkboxes.
Q9	In your opinion, what are the biggest challenges in implementing the principles of the LGPD during software development?	Open.
Q10	In your opinion, what are the best techniques/practices that guarantee the privacy and data protection required by the LGPD?	Open.
Q11	Can you describe in detail how your team mitigates the challenges of complying with the LGPD?	Open.
Q12	If you have anything to add, please use this question.	Open.